

The Need to Adapt Publication Formats

Concepts of the ICUC Study Group

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Fracture Treatment Study Group

Continuous Changes in Scientific Publishing

The world of scientific publishing, especially in clinical surgery, is constantly evolving. There are several parallel and interconnected trends that deserve consideration:

1. Internal Medicine vs. Surgery

There is a considerable, and possibly growing, gap between the evidence base in internal medicine and surgery. One major challenge is the lack of homogeneity among clinical trial groups. This is compounded by the near-absence of comprehensive intra-operative photo documentation, which is essential for secondary analysis of technical performance quality—an outcome factor that varies significantly. (1, 5, 9, 10, 11)

2. The Young Generation of Surgeons

The habits of the younger generation of surgeons in relation to reading scientific literature have dramatically changed. After basic training, traditional textbooks and lengthy papers no longer serve as the preferred sources for knowledge acquisition. Instead, short, focused, and easily digestible information modules, online resources, and tailored content are favored. These formats must be easily integrated into busy schedules and align with the modern work-life balance. Furthermore, individualized learning has become the preferred mode of continuous education.

3. Evolution of Information Technology (IT)

Another significant trend is the rise of open-source products, which respond to the increasing demand for easy access to real-world data. Clinical research data are becoming more accessible, but the volume of available data now exceeds the capacity of conventional publication formats.

Possible Adaptations

The ICUC Study Group (2, 3) has developed a concept for comprehensive intra-operative photo documentation of orthopedic trauma surgery procedures. These case series, gathered from international centers, consist of complete, consecutive, unaltered, and anonymized cases that represent real-world data. These cases can be analyzed secondarily to evaluate technical performance (4, 6, 7, 8).

The discussion around adapting "knowledge dissemination formats" aligns with the preferences of the new generation of surgeons and is therefore warranted (4). The ICUC group believes that changing the format of publications is a valuable step in addressing the challenges outlined above.

Proposal for Possible Adaptations of Publication Formats

We propose an adaptation of publication formats based on three components:

A: Peer-reviewed, concise articles addressing well-defined clinical problems, illustrated by one or more documented, typical examples. These articles would include a hyperlink to a repository containing a substantial number of consecutive, unselected, fully documented similar cases (cf. C) and a corresponding bibliography.

B: A video presentation on the research topic, available on an educational platform, including instructions on how to access the data repository (cf. C).

C: Easy access to a series of consecutive, unchanged, anonymized, and completely documented cases stored on the ICUC repository (www.icucplus.net / www.icuctags.net / www.icuc.net). These cases would resemble the examples presented in section A and could be retrieved using the ICUC search tool (<https://www.vumedi.com/video/revisiting-the-icuc-concept-including-a-powerful-search-tool-by-jesse-jupiter/>).

Visual Examples

zenodo Search records... Communities My dashboard

Published August 20, 2024 | Version v1 Data paper Open

Artificial Experience (AE) in Decision-Making for Displaced Greater Tuberosity in Four-Part Proximal Humerus Fracture

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Detailed case analysis, potentially facilitated by Artificial Experience, could aid surgeons in making more informed decisions.

Are limitations in abduction and external rotation, along with shoulder pain due to subacromial impingement, expected outcomes after a displaced, non-reduced greater tuberosity in a four-part proximal humerus fracture, or are they outcomes that may or may not occur?

Files

Artificial Experience (AE) in Decision-Making for Displaced Greater Tuberosity in Four-Part Proximal Humerus Fracture.pdf

Page: 6 of 7 Full Width

A) Reduced Joint step
11-VI-155 / 30y Female
PRE 22w 30w
ICUC Score at 30w FLO P0

B) Not-reduced Joint step
11-VI-456 / 65y
PRE 104w
No ICUC Score

C) Not-reduced Joint step
11-VI-847 / 55y Male
PRE 79w

Fig. 1: Short article on the research topic. <https://zenodo.org/records/13350778>

ICUC Database+
Including a Search tool

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EMAIL JESSE B.

ICUC **Revisiting the ICUC concept including a powerful Search Tool by Jesse Jupiter**
By ICUC FEATURING JESSE B. JUPITER

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Fig. 2: Video presentation on the referenced research topic, available on a video-education platform.
<https://www.vumedi.com/video/revisiting-the-icuc-concept-including-a-powerful-search-tool-by-jesse-jupiter/>

Fig. 3: Easy access to a series of consecutive, unchanged, anonymized, and completely documented cases on the ICUC repository. www.icuctags.net

Summary

The combination of “information packages”—including peer-reviewed short papers, easy access to comprehensive data via repositories, and video presentations on educational platforms—appears to align with the needs of the new generation of surgeons. This approach also takes into account the rapid changes in information technology and how data are accessed and disseminated.

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- Problems cannot be solved by the same way of thinking that has caused them!
- If you cannot explain it simply, you did not understand it well enough!

Albert Einstein